

A COMPARISON OF FREE SPACE AND FIBER MIXER PERFORMANCES IN A HETERODYNE LASER RADAR

Martin B. Mark, PhD, Major, USAF

USAF Wright Laboratory, WL/AARI-2, Wright-Patterson AFB, OH 45433

I. Abstract

A conventional heterodyne laser radar system employs mixing between the signal field and the local oscillator (LO) fields in free space. In such a system not all the optical power collected by the receiving aperture contributes to the power in the intermediate frequency (IF) signal. Only that portion of the received power which is in the same temporal and spatial mode as the LO will contribute to the IF signal. In a heterodyne detection system employing a single mode fiber mixer, the signal and LO fields are perfectly matched inside the fiber, so all the signal power propagating in the fiber will contribute to the IF signal. However, not all the power focused onto the end of a single mode optical fiber will couple into the fiber's single propagating mode. In order to compare a heterodyne system employing free space mixing between the LO and the received field with a heterodyne system employing mixing in a fiber coupler, we need to compare the IF signal-to-noise ratio (CNR) from each system for identical system design parameters. The greatest obstacle to making this comparison is calculating what fraction of the received optical power actually couples into the fiber. This paper performs that calculation and compares the resulting CNRs. The comparison indicates the fiber mixer will generally under-perform the free space mixer unless the f-numbers of the receiver optics and the single mode fiber are approximately matched. In this case the fiber mixer performs as well as the free space mixer and can even out-perform it for some optics designs.

II. Free Space Mixer Performance

The IF signal power from a free space mixing system is not difficult to calculate. All the equations necessary to make the computation are already well known and the following discussion merely collects those results into a form suitable to solve our specific problem. Figure 1 is a block diagram of both the fiber and free space mixing systems.

We will match the local oscillator (LO) field (referenced to the transmitting aperture) to the transmitted field and define the fields at the transmitting aperture as¹:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{U}_T(\bar{\rho}, t) &= \sqrt{P_T} \underline{s}(t) \underline{\xi}(\bar{\rho}), \\ \underline{U}_{LO}(\bar{\rho}, t) &= \sqrt{P_{LO}} e^{j2\pi\nu_{IF}t} \underline{\xi}(\bar{\rho}) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where P_T is the transmitted power, P_{LO} is the LO power, $\underline{\xi}(\bar{\rho})$ is the transmitted beam shape at the transmitter aperture plane, normalized to unit area, $\underline{s}(t)$ is the transmitted pulse shape normalized to unity time average power, and ν_{IF} is the IF frequency in Hz.

It is customary in much of the laser radar literature to write the detector IF current as a target plane integral by back propagating the LO field to the target [1]. Doing this, the signal component of the IF current out of the detector is [2]:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{y}(t) &= \frac{q\eta}{h\nu_o} \frac{1}{(\lambda L)^2} \iint_{A_t} d\bar{\rho} \tilde{T}(\bar{\rho}, t - \frac{L}{c}) \cdot \\ &\underline{U}_T(\frac{\bar{\rho}}{\lambda L}, t - \frac{2L}{c}) \cdot \underline{U}_{LO}^*(\frac{\bar{\rho}}{\lambda L}, t) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where q is the electronic charge, η is the detector quantum efficiency, h is Planck's constant, ν_o is the optical frequency, λ is the wavelength of the light, L is the range to the target, c is the velocity of light, $c = \lambda\nu_o$, A_t is the target area, $\tilde{T}(\bar{\rho}, t)$ is the target's random, complex reflectivity, and $\underline{U}_T(\bar{\rho}/\lambda L, t)$ and $\underline{U}_{LO}(\bar{\rho}/\lambda L, t)$ are the Fourier transforms of the transmitted and LO fields, respectively, evaluated at spatial frequency $\bar{\rho}/\lambda L$.

Let the transmitted beam shape, $\underline{\xi}(\bar{\rho})$, be the usual Gaussian function with a $1/e^2$ beam power radius of w_o , normalized to unit area and let the

¹In this paper, an underscore means the variable is the complex envelope of the real variable, an overscore indicates a vector, and a tilde ($\tilde{}$) over a variable indicates it is random.

transmitting aperture A_T be large enough that it does not appreciably truncate the transmitted beam or the LO. Then the the beam shape and its Fourier transform are:

$$\underline{\xi}(\bar{\rho}) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi w_o^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{|\bar{\rho}|^2}{w_o^2}\right) \quad (3)$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{\bar{\rho}'}\{\underline{\xi}(\bar{\rho}')\} \Big|_{\frac{\bar{\rho}}{\lambda L}} = \sqrt{2\pi w_o^2} \exp\left(-\left(\frac{\pi w_o}{\lambda L}\right)^2 |\bar{\rho}|^2\right).$$

For a stationary, purely speckle target the target statistics are [2],[3]:

$$\begin{aligned} E[\tilde{\mathcal{I}}(\bar{\rho}_1)] &= 0, & E[\tilde{\mathcal{I}}(\bar{\rho}_1)\tilde{\mathcal{I}}(\bar{\rho}_2)] &= 0, \\ E[\tilde{\mathcal{I}}(\bar{\rho}_1)\tilde{\mathcal{I}}^*(\bar{\rho}_2)] &= \lambda^2 \mathcal{F}_s(\bar{\rho}_1)\delta(\bar{\rho}_1 - \bar{\rho}_2), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $E[\]$ indicates a statistical expectation (average) over the random variable or process and $\mathcal{F}_s(\bar{\rho})$ is related to the reflectance of the target at coordinate $\bar{\rho}$. For a uniform target, \mathcal{F}_s is related to the commonly used diffuse target reflectivity, ρ_s , by $\mathcal{F}_s = \frac{\rho_s}{\pi}$ [3]. If the target is resolved by the transmitter aperture (*i.e.*, the illuminator beam extent at the target is less than the target area), is range unresolved, approximately stationary over T , and uniform over the area illuminated by the transmitted beam and the time lags (the $t - \frac{L}{c}$ and $t - \frac{2L}{c}$ effects) are negligible, we can use these statistics and the given beam shape to find the mean, time-average (indicated by the notation $\langle \ \rangle$), IF signal power:

$$\langle E[|\tilde{y}(t)|^2] \rangle = \left(\frac{q\eta}{h\nu_o}\right)^2 P_{LO} \lambda^2 \mathcal{F}_s P_T \pi \left(\frac{w_o}{\lambda L}\right)^2. \quad (5)$$

To find the carrier-to-noise ratio (CNR) out of the detector, assume the post-detection filter bandwidth, B_N , is greater than the bandwidth of the transmitted waveform $\underline{s}(t)$ and divide by the expected value of the LO shot noise component, $(q^2\eta/h\nu_o)P_{LO}B_N$ [4]:

$$\text{CNR}_{fs} = \frac{\eta}{h\nu_o B_N} P_T \mathcal{F}_s \frac{\pi w_o^2}{L^2}. \quad (6)$$

We will compare this with the CNR from a fiber mixing system, CNR_{fb} , for identical system parameters η , B_N , P_T , \mathcal{F}_s , w_o , L , and A_T .

It is interesting to examine this CNR in the following manner. The first portion of the CNR expression, $\eta/h\nu_o B_N$, is just the inverse of the IF LO shot noise power. Therefore, the remainder of the CNR expression, $P_T \mathcal{F}_s \pi w_o^2 / L^2$, is the IF signal power. However, the expected value of the total power collected by the receiving aperture is:

$$E[\tilde{P}_c] = P_T \cdot \frac{\rho_s}{\pi} \cdot \frac{A_R}{L^2} = P_T \mathcal{F}_s \frac{A_R}{L^2}. \quad (7)$$

Obviously, only a portion of the power collected by

the receiver aperture actually contributes to the IF CNR. Dividing the last two quantities, assuming a monostatic system (so $A_R \equiv A_T$), and using $w_o = d_T/4$, (the maximum usable value of w_o for which beam truncation is negligible), gives:

$$\frac{\pi w_o^2}{A_R} = \frac{1}{4}. \quad (8)$$

In other words, in a free-space mixing system sensing a purely speckle target, only $\frac{1}{4}$ of the collected optical power actually contributes to improving the IF CNR. The remaining collected optical power is in spatial modes which do not mix with the LO spatial mode. It is possible to improve on the percentage of power which contributes to the IF CNR by using a Gaussian beam with a w_o which is a larger fraction of d_T , but this leads to beam truncation, increased beam divergence in the far field, and the above equation no longer accurately predicts the coupling efficiency to the IF. Rye and Frehlich have shown, however, that even with the optimum choice of w_o for a given d_T , the maximum efficiency when using truncated Gaussian beams is limited to about 44% [5]. Similarly, using $d_T/w_o > 4$ will reduce the mixing efficiency to even less than $\frac{1}{4}$.

III. Fiber Mixer Performance

A. General analysis

Now compute the IF signal power for the fiber mixing system. Since the local oscillator and the received optical field will be propagating in the same single mode fiber, their field patterns must be identical. A single mode fiber will only propagate one field pattern, called the HE_{11} mode. Designate this normalized field pattern $\underline{U}_{11}(\bar{\rho})$. The signal component of the IF current out of the detector is:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{y}(t) &= \frac{q\eta}{h\nu_o} \iint_{A_d} d\bar{\rho} \left(\sqrt{\tilde{P}_f} \underline{U}_{11}(\bar{\rho}) \underline{s}(t - \frac{2L}{c}) \right) \\ &\quad \left(\sqrt{P_{LO}} \underline{U}_{11}^*(\bar{\rho}) e^{-j2\pi\nu_{IF}t} \right) \\ &= \frac{q\eta}{h\nu_o} \sqrt{P_{LO} \tilde{P}_f} \underline{s}(t - \frac{2L}{c}) e^{-j2\pi\nu_{IF}t}, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where \tilde{P}_f is the received optical power coupled into and propagating in the fiber, and A_d is the detector area (which is much larger than the mode field extent). \tilde{P}_f is a random variable because of target speckle. Consequently, the mean, time-average IF signal power and CNR are:

$$\langle E[|\tilde{y}(t)|^2] \rangle = \left(\frac{q\eta}{h\nu_o}\right)^2 P_{LO} E[\tilde{P}_f] \Rightarrow \quad (10)$$

$$\text{CNR}_{\text{fib}} = \frac{\eta}{h\nu_o B_N} E[\tilde{P}_f],$$

and all the received power coupled into the fiber contributes to the mean, time-average IF signal power. It now only remains to compute $E[\tilde{P}_f]$.

To compute \tilde{P}_f , propagate the transmitted field $\underline{U}_T(\bar{\rho})$ to the target using the free space Green's function, assume far field operation ($A_T \ll \lambda L$), and multiply by the target's complex reflectivity, $\underline{T}(\bar{\rho})$. Back propagate the resulting field to the receiving aperture using the same Green's function and then through the lens to its focal plane. This will give us the field at the lens' focal plane, $\tilde{U}_f(\bar{\rho}_f)$, in terms of the target and system characteristics. The end of the fiber will be at the lens' focal plane where it will collect whatever power it can from the field. The result is:

$$\tilde{U}_f(\bar{\rho}_f) = \frac{1}{(j\lambda f)(\lambda L)^2} \iint_{A_t} d\bar{\rho} \tilde{T}(\bar{\rho}, t - \frac{L}{c}) \cdot \underline{u}_{T(\frac{\bar{\rho}}{\lambda L}, t - \frac{2L}{c})} \mathcal{W}_R\left(-\frac{\bar{\rho} - \frac{L}{f}\bar{\rho}_f}{\lambda L}\right) \quad (11)$$

where f is the focal length of the receiving lens and $\mathcal{W}_R(\bar{\omega})$ is the Fourier transform of the receiving aperture function, $W_R(\bar{\rho})$. ($W_R(\bar{\rho})$ is 1 where the aperture is clear and 0 where it is opaque.)

In words, this formula represents an image of the target in the focal plane of the lens, with illumination given by the far field pattern of the transmitted beam, and with the image blurred by the diffraction introduced by receiving aperture's Fourier transform. (This is easiest to see by letting the receiving aperture be infinitely large so the function $\mathcal{W}_R(\cdot)$ becomes a Dirac delta function.)

This is the field outside the fiber face. Inside the fiber face, the field is that of the HE_{11} mode of a dielectric waveguide. The field distribution of this mode is proportional to $J_0(r)$ in the fiber core (where r is the radial distance from the center of the fiber) and proportional to $K_0(r)$ in the fiber cladding, where $J_0(\cdot)$ is the zero order Bessel function and $K_0(\cdot)$ is the zero order modified Bessel function. Fortunately, however, Marcuse [6],[7] has shown that a Gaussian function very accurately approximates the field distribution. Therefore, the normalized single mode field distribution is approximately:

$$\underline{U}_{11}(\bar{\rho}) \approx \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi w^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{|\bar{\rho}|^2}{w^2}\right), \quad (12)$$

where Marcuse also shows the optimum choice for the parameter w is given empirically by the equation:

$$w \equiv r_c g_o(V) = r_c \left(0.65 + \frac{1.619}{V^{3/2}} + \frac{2.879}{V^6}\right), \quad (13)$$

where r_c is the fiber core radius and V is the

normalized frequency in the fiber, $V \equiv kr_c \sqrt{n_1^2 - n_2^2}$ (where n_1 is the index of the core material and n_2 is the index of the cladding material).

Snyder [8] has shown that it is possible to approximate the coupling coefficient between a field in free-space and a fiber mode with an overlap integral. Using Snyder's general formula, the above relations, and rearranging the integrals, the power coupled into the fiber is:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{P}_f &\approx \left| \iint d\bar{r} \tilde{U}_f(\bar{r}) \underline{U}_{11}^*(\bar{r}) \right|^2 \\ &= \left| \frac{1}{(j\lambda f)(\lambda L)^2} \iint_{A_t} d\bar{\rho} \tilde{T}(\bar{\rho}) \underline{u}_{T(\frac{\bar{\rho}}{\lambda L})} \cdot \mathcal{F}\left\{W_R(\bar{\rho}_1) \underline{u}_{11}^*\left(-\frac{\bar{\rho}_1}{\lambda f}\right)\right\} \right|_{-\frac{\bar{\rho}}{\lambda L}} \right|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Defining the truncated or apertured version of the fiber field mode by the term:

$$\underline{u}_{11t}^*\left(\frac{\bar{\rho}}{\lambda L}\right) \equiv \mathcal{F}_{\bar{\rho}_1}\left\{W_R(\bar{\rho}_1) \underline{u}_{11}^*\left(-\frac{\bar{\rho}_1}{\lambda f}\right)\right\} \Big|_{-\frac{\bar{\rho}}{\lambda L}}, \quad (15)$$

and using it in the previous equation gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{P}_f &\approx \left| \frac{1}{(j\lambda f)(\lambda L)^2} \iint_{A_t} d\bar{\rho} \tilde{T}(\bar{\rho}) \cdot \underline{u}_{T(\frac{\bar{\rho}}{\lambda L})} \underline{u}_{11t}^*\left(\frac{\bar{\rho}}{\lambda L}\right) \right|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

This equation has a very satisfying and intuitively appealing form. It is easy to see how the form of this equation is very similar to the integral portion of equation (2) for $\tilde{y}(t)$ for the free space mixing system. The first term here is the target, exactly the same as the free space integral. The second term is the transmitter illumination propagated to the target plane, exactly the same as the free space integral. In the free space integral, the remaining term is the local oscillator, referenced to the receiver aperture, back propagated to the target plane. Here the last term is the fiber mode field back propagated to the receiver aperture, truncated by the receiver aperture, and then the result back propagated to the target.

Using the target statistics of equation (4), taking the expectation of \tilde{P}_f , making the change of variables

$$\bar{\rho}_o \equiv \frac{\bar{\rho}'_1 + \bar{\rho}'_2}{2}, \quad \Delta\bar{\rho} \equiv \bar{\rho}'_1 - \bar{\rho}'_2 \quad (17)$$

and doing a significant amount of algebra gives:

$$E[\tilde{P}_f] \approx \frac{\mathcal{T}_s}{f^2(\lambda L)^4} \iint_{A_t} d\bar{\rho} \left| \underline{u}_{T(\frac{\bar{\rho}}{\lambda L})} \right|^2 \left| \underline{u}_{11t}^*\left(\frac{\bar{\rho}}{\lambda L}\right) \right|^2$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\simeq \frac{\mathcal{T}_s}{f^2(\lambda L)^2} \iint d\overline{\Delta\rho} \mathcal{T}_\rho \left\{ \left| \underline{u}_T \left(\frac{\overline{\rho}}{\lambda L} \right) \right|^2 \right\} \left| \frac{\overline{\Delta\rho}}{\Delta\rho} \right| \\ &\int \int d\overline{\rho}_o W_R \left(\overline{\rho}_o + \frac{1}{2}\overline{\Delta\rho} \right) \underline{u}_{11}^* \left(-\frac{\overline{\rho}_o + \frac{1}{2}\overline{\Delta\rho}}{\lambda f} \right) \\ &W_R \left(\overline{\rho}_o - \frac{1}{2}\overline{\Delta\rho} \right) \underline{u}_{11} \left(-\frac{\overline{\rho}_o - \frac{1}{2}\overline{\Delta\rho}}{\lambda f} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

This is about as far as the expression can go without giving the field and aperture functions some specific forms.

B. General circular aperture

Now let the apertures have the usual circular shape with diameter d_R :

$$W_R(\overline{\rho}) = \text{circ} \left(\frac{\overline{\rho}}{d_R} \right) \equiv \begin{cases} 1 & |\overline{\rho}| \leq d_R/2 \\ 0 & |\overline{\rho}| > d_R/2 \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

let the transmitted beam be the usual Gaussian shape, as before and the fiber mode field is as shown in equation (12). Plugging all this into equation (18), simplifying, and scaling the space variables by d_R gives:

$$\begin{aligned} E[\tilde{P}_f] &\simeq \frac{4\mathcal{T}_s P_T d_R^2}{\pi L^2} a^2 \\ &\int \int d\overline{\Delta\rho} \cdot \exp \left(-\left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{d_R}{w_o} \right)^2 + a^2 \right) |\overline{\Delta\rho}|^2 \right) \\ &\int \int d\overline{\rho}_o e^{-4a^2 |\overline{\rho}_o|^2} \text{circ} \left(\overline{\rho}_o + \frac{1}{2}\overline{\Delta\rho} \right) \text{circ} \left(\overline{\rho}_o - \frac{1}{2}\overline{\Delta\rho} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where the parameter a^2 is defined by the relation:

$$a^2 \equiv \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{\pi w d_R}{\lambda f} \right)^2. \quad (21)$$

This is a useful parameter because it appears repeatedly in the expression for $E[\tilde{P}_f]$ and it is proportional to the fiber design parameter w/λ and inversely proportional to the system optics f-number, f/d_R .

The two exponentials are just standard Gaussian functions centered at the origins of the $\overline{\rho}_o$ - and $\overline{\Delta\rho}$ -planes. The $\text{circ}()$ functions, however, are unit diameter circles centered at $\pm \frac{1}{2}\overline{\Delta\rho}$ in the $\overline{\rho}_o$ -plane and the $\overline{\rho}_o$ -integral is just over the area of overlap of the two $\text{circ}()$ functions. If $|\overline{\Delta\rho}| > 1$, however, the two $\text{circ}()$ functions will not overlap at all and the entire equation is identically equal to zero. Figure 2 depicts a graph of $\text{circ}(\overline{\rho}_o + \frac{1}{2}\overline{\Delta\rho})$ and $\text{circ}(\overline{\rho}_o - \frac{1}{2}\overline{\Delta\rho})$ in the $\overline{\rho}_o$ -plane for an arbitrary $\overline{\Delta\rho}$. Notice the area of overlap will always be centered at the origin of the $\overline{\rho}_o$ -plane. The area of the overlap is dependent only on $|\overline{\Delta\rho}|$ and not on the angle of $\overline{\Delta\rho}$. Furthermore, since the Gaussian function in $\overline{\rho}_o$ is circulo-symmetric, the inner integral over the $\overline{\rho}_o$ -plane will also be

independent of the angle of $\overline{\Delta\rho}$.

Figure 3 depicts one quadrant of the $\overline{\rho}_o$ -plane for the specific case where $\overline{\Delta\rho}$ lies on the y-axis, $\overline{\Delta\rho} = (0, -|\overline{\Delta\rho}|)$, so the center of the circle whose arc is depicted in figure 3 is at coordinates $(x_c, y_c) = (0, -|\overline{\Delta\rho}|/2)$. From the equation for a circle with center at (x_c, y_c) and radius r :

$$(x - x_c)^2 + (y - y_c)^2 = r^2, \quad (22)$$

it is easy to find values for the coordinates on the x- and y-axes of the arbitrary point on the edge of the overlap area, (x_o, y_o) , shown in figure 3:

$$\begin{aligned} x_{max} &= \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{1 - |\overline{\Delta\rho}|^2} & y_{max} &= \frac{1}{2} (1 - |\overline{\Delta\rho}|) \\ y_o &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{1 - 4x_o^2} - |\overline{\Delta\rho}| \right). \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Since the inner integral over the $\overline{\rho}_o$ -plane does not depend on the direction of $\overline{\Delta\rho}$, it is possible to simply select a convenient direction for $\overline{\Delta\rho}$ and perform the integration for that direction. Figure 3 depicts one convenient such choice. For this choice of $\overline{\Delta\rho}$, the integral over the entire plane is just four times (since there are four quadrants) the integral over the area shown in the figure.

Separating the integration in the $\overline{\rho}_o$ -plane into x- and y-integrals, converting the outer integral to polar coordinates, dividing by the IF LO noise power and then the free space CNR, the ratio of the CNRs is:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\text{CNR}_{\text{fib}}}{\text{CNR}_{\text{fs}}} &= \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \left(\frac{d_R}{w_o} \right)^2 \\ &\int_0^1 du \exp \left[-\left(\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{d_R}{w_o} \right)^2 + a^2 \right) u \right] \\ &\int_0^{\alpha\sqrt{1-u}} dx e^{-x^2} \text{erf} \left(\sqrt{a^2 - x^2} - \alpha\sqrt{u} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

where $\text{erf}()$ is the standard error function from statistics, $\text{erf}(x) \equiv \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x dy e^{-y^2}$.

There are two parameters in this expression, d_R/w_o and a . Since the $\exp()$ function and the $\text{erf}()$ function are both very smooth functions and they fall off rapidly as a function of increasing arguments, the integrals are not too difficult or time consuming to do numerically.

C. Numerical analysis results

Figure 4 is a plot of the CNR ratio, in dB, as a function of the a parameter for three values of d_R/w_o , 4.0 (the minimum useful value), 7.0, and 10.0. Notice the fiber system is always worse than the free space system except for a small region around an

a parameter of about two where the improvement is on the order of a few dB or less. At least part of this improvement may be illusory, however. The approximations involved in forming equations (12) and (14) are limited in their accuracy. In fact, Marcuse [9], in plotting his figure 6, found a similar excess performance peak problem when using exactly these same two approximations. Here, however, as the ratio d_R/w_o gets larger, the performance improvement becomes more pronounced. This may be because as d_R/w_o gets larger, the LO-received field matching, as given by equation (8) gets worse, whereas the fiber field-received field matching may remain at its optimum point with the appropriate choice of parameter a . In effect, the choice of the fiber design provides an additional parameter to vary in order to optimize the field coupling. Unfortunately, this is more a testimony to the poor coupling for large values of d_R/w_o than a praise for the fiber mixer. In practice there may be some applications where a large d_R/w_o ratio would be useful. An example might be a high resolution radar (hence the large d_R) which used flood light illumination of the target (hence the small w_o). However, for cases where the design keeps d_R/w_o as small as possible, it seems the free space mixer makes the best possible use of the collected backscattered power and the fiber mixer cannot significantly improve on the free space mixer's performance.

Now investigate what sort of fiber and optics design the optimum a value requires. The ratio w/λ is defined by:

$$\frac{w}{\lambda} \equiv \frac{r_c}{\lambda} g_o(V) = \frac{V g_o(V)}{2\pi\sqrt{2n\Delta n}} = \frac{V g_o(V)}{2\pi(NA)} \quad (25)$$

where NA is the usual numerical aperture for a fiber. However, for a single mode fiber, the range of V values of interest for is just $1.5 < V < 2.4$. Within this range, the factor $V g_o(V)$ is numerically almost constant. It varies only from 2.676 (for $V = 1.5$) to 2.641 (for $V = 2.4$). If we approximate it by $V g_o(V) \simeq 2.66$, we find $w/\lambda \simeq 0.42/NA$ and we can write:

$$a \simeq \frac{0.94}{(NA)(f/\#)} \quad (26)$$

where $f/\# \equiv f/d_R$ is the standard physical optics f-number. The optical f-number, however, is just the inverse of twice the numerical aperture. Therefore we can write:

$$a \simeq 1.9 \frac{(NA)_{\text{optics}}}{(NA)_{\text{fiber}}} \quad (27)$$

From figure 4 we notice the optimum chose of a is about 2 for a wide range of d_R/w_o values. Our last equation, however, tells us an a value of about 2

corresponds to the point where the numerical apertures of the optics and the fiber are approximately matched. This is exactly what we would expect, however, from simple geometrical optics reasoning! Furthermore, since reasonable single mode fibers have small numerical aperture, we will require receiver optics with a reasonably large f-number in order to optimize the coupling. This is an fortuitous result since the larger the optics f-number, the easier it is to fabricate the optics with low aberrations.

As an example calculation, return to equation (27) and use $a = 2$ as the optimal value. Then we get the best performance when

$$f/\# \simeq \frac{1}{2(NA)_{\text{fiber}}} \quad (28)$$

It is common to write the numerical aperture of the fiber in the following form:

$$(NA)_{\text{fiber}} = \sqrt{n_1^2 - n_2^2} \simeq n_1 \sqrt{2\Delta} \quad (29)$$

where $\Delta \equiv \frac{n_1 - n_2}{n_1}$. Reasonable values for Δ and n_1 (the fiber core index of refraction) for a single mode fiber are $\Delta = 0.003$ and $n_1 = 1.5$ which gives $NA \simeq 0.12$ and $f/\# \simeq 4.3$.

IV. Summary and Conclusions

This paper compared the CNR at the IF stage of a heterodyne laser radar receiver employing the traditional free space mixer with the IF CNR from a heterodyne laser radar receiver employing a fiber mixer stage. The analysis shows that the fiber mixer will achieve optimum performance when the fiber's numerical aperture is approximately matched to the receiving optics numerical aperture. This is exactly the result one would expect from simple geometric optics reasoning. When the fiber and receiving optics are optimized, the fiber mixer will still perform, at best, only marginally better than the free space mixer. The greatest improvement will occur in cases where the system requirements force an inefficient use of the aperture by the transmitting beam. In this case, the fiber mixer can compensate somewhat for the loss of mixing efficiency encountered with an over size aperture. Apparently the free space mixer makes nearly optimal use of the collected optical radiation even though the mixing efficiency is 25% or less.

Since single mode fibers always have quite small numerical apertures, the optimal receiving optics in a fiber mixer may have a reasonable f-number. A typical value would be around $f/\# \sim 4$. This does, however, pose an additional constraint on the optical system design. If it is not possible to use the optimal f-number optics, it is possible to use the relations derived, figure 4 in particular, to determine how much of a reduction in mixing efficiency will result.

V. References

1. Siegman, A. E. "The Antenna Properties of Optical Heterodyne Receivers." *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 54, no. 10, October 1966, pp. 1350 - 1356.
2. Shapiro, J. H., B. A. Capron, and R. C. Harney. "Image and target detection with a heterodyne-reception optical radar." *Applied Optics*, 20, no. 19, 1 October 1981, pp. 3292 - 3313.
3. Shapiro, Jeffrey H. "Target Reflectivity Theory for Coherent Laser Radars." *Applied Optics*, 21, 15 September 1982.
4. Gagliardi, Robert M. and Sherman Karp. *Optical Communications*. John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1976.
5. Rye, Barry J. and Rod G. Frehlich, "The truncated Gaussian lidar antenna problem revisited," in *Technical Digest on Coherent Laser Radar: Technology and Applications, 1991* (Optical Society of America, Washington, DC, 1991), 12, pp 165-168.

6. Marcuse, D. "Loss Analysis of Single-Mode Fiber Splices." *The Bell System Technical Journal*, 56, no. 5, May - June 1977, pp. 703 - 718.
7. Marcuse, D. "Gaussian approximation of the fundamental modes of graded-index fibers." *Journal of the Optical Society of America*, 68, no. 1, January 1978, pp. 103 - 109.
8. Snyder, Allan W. "Excitation and Scattering of Modes on a Dielectric or Optical Fiber." *IEEE Transaction on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, MTT-17, no. 12, December 1969, pp. 1138 - 1144.
9. Marcuse, Dietrich. "Excitation of the Dominant Mode of a Round Fiber by a Gaussian Beam." *Bell System Technical Journal*, 49, October 1970, pp 1695-1703.

Figure 2
Circ() Function Overlap

Figure 3
Circ() Function Coordinates

Figure 4
CNR ratio -vs- a parameter

